

LESSON AS THE MAIN FORM OF EDUCATION AT SCHOOL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7440534>

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ELSEVIER

Received: 13-12-2022

Accepted: 15-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Abstract: This article discusses the forms of organization of the educational process and the distinctive features of the classroom-based learning system, the founder of which is Y.A.Kamensky.

Keywords: lesson, learning process, learning system, educational subject, students, training course, school..

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There are many forms of organization of the educational process. Each of them has its own distinctive features, and at the same time they are all interconnected by a class-based learning system, the founder of which is Y.A.Kamensky.

With a class-time system, educational work is carried out in classes with a permanent composition of students, at certain hours, overtime, in various academic subjects. This system of education in its main features is currently accepted both in our schools and in schools of other countries.

Each lesson is a part of the content of a training course on a particular academic subject and has a certain didactic purpose, which is determined by the place of this lesson in the course, section, topic on a particular academic subject.

With a classroom-based learning system, educational work is carried out with all students at the same time. It can be of a general class, group or individual nature.

The class-based system adopted at the school allows:

- 1) evenly distribute the study of a training course on a particular subject into certain parts—lessons that follow each other in a strict logical sequence according to a schedule within the precisely allotted study time;
- 2) systematically carry out the leading role of the teacher in the education, upbringing and development of students;
- 3) to organize educational work taking into account the psychological characteristics of mastering knowledge, skills, skills in their unity with the formation of personality;
- 4) alternate work and rest of students and thereby contribute to the introduction of a certain clarity in the work of the school;

5) формировать коллективистические отношения.

At the same time, there are some disadvantages inherent in the class-class system, in particular, equating a certain "average student" in the lesson. Strong and weak students suffer from this. The former are forced to "stand still", they cannot fully use their strength and capabilities; the latter do not keep up with their comrades, begin to lag behind in their studies, sometimes they become unsuccessful and repeaters.

The elimination of this shortcoming is a task of paramount importance in the conditions of universal secondary education. Types and structure of lessons. The term structure is of Latin origin, it means the mutual disposition and connection of the components of something, the structure.

The structure of the lesson, i.e. the relative position of its components, depends on what place it occupies in the general system of lessons on the topic of the course. Each lesson is an organizationally, logically and psychologically complete whole. The organizational integrity and completeness of the lesson consists in the fact that the lesson begins and ends at a strictly defined time, the students and the teacher are ready for the lesson, the students are skillfully organized for work throughout it, the time is distributed clearly and rationally.

Logical integrity finds its expression in a certain content of the lesson, divided into separate questions that reveal the outline of the topic, its logical structure. Psychological integrity is characterized by the need to achieve a goal, a sense of satisfaction from successful results, desire and desire for further advancement.

In other words, the intellectual, emotional and volitional forces of students are activated in the classroom. In a good lesson, the organizational, logical and psychological sides are interrelated. However, in practice, there are facts when the lesson is organizationally finished, but logically and psychologically not finished (no conclusion has been drawn, no rule has been formulated; students were not active in the lesson, they had no questions, no interest in what they were studying, no sense of educational satisfaction). Such a lesson, of course, cannot be considered good.

Representing a complete whole, each lesson at the same time is a link in a single chain of lessons on the topic of the educational subject. Therefore, for the correct construction of any lesson, it is necessary to understand the entire system of lessons on this topic and the place of a separate lesson in this system. This is necessary in order to see the perspective of their activities, clearly present the logical content, educational and educational significance of the topic as a whole and, on this basis, determine the main didactic purpose of each lesson, how the educational and educational tasks of the topic will be concretized in each lesson.

To determine the main didactic purpose of the lesson means to establish what it will mainly be devoted to – whether the study of new material, consolidation,

repetition, systematization of educational material, or checking and accounting for the assimilation of educational material. The lesson may have several didactic purposes. Depending on what the main didactic goal is solved in a particular lesson, the structure of the lessons, and therefore the types of lessons will be different.

The pedagogical literature offers various classifications of lesson types, but there is no generally accepted classification. Nevertheless, most didactics believe that it is necessary to classify the types of lessons on the basis of the main didactic purpose of the lesson.

Based on the main didactic purpose of the lesson, you can specify the following types of lessons: a combined or combined lesson; a lesson of learning new; a lesson of consolidation; a lesson of repetition, or a repeating-generalizing lesson; a lesson of testing knowledge, skills, skills – a control or accounting lesson.

Combined lesson.

In this type of lessons, several didactic tasks are solved: repetition of the completed and checking homework, studying and consolidating new knowledge. Combined lessons are especially widespread in the lower grades of school. This is explained both by the age characteristics of younger schoolchildren (instability of attention, increased emotional excitability), and by the peculiarity of building new curricula and textbooks.

In particular, the peculiarity of mathematics textbooks is that they are built over time, and most importantly, each lesson provides for work on several lines: work on previously acquired knowledge in order to repeat and consolidate them, work on learning new knowledge and consolidating it, work on material preparing for the assimilation of new knowledge.

The structure of combined type lessons can be as follows:

- 1) checking homework,
- 2) preparation for the assimilation of new knowledge,
- 3) explanation of the new material,
- 4) consolidation of the studied material,
- 5) homework assignment.

A slightly different arrangement of the components of the combined lesson is also possible. For example:

- 1) learning new material,
- 2) consolidation of what has been studied in this lesson and previously passed,
- 3) homework assignment,
- 4) preparatory work for the study of a new topic.

In a combined type of lesson, its components – repetition or verification, study and consolidation of a new one – are presented more or less evenly in their volume and time.

A lesson in learning new things.

Lessons of this type in their pure form are rare. This is due to the uniqueness of the educational material and the instability of the attention of students. New material is considered in small parts in almost every lesson. But there are lessons in which the study of new material is the main didactic goal. This work is given most of the time in the lesson, all other parts of the lesson are also subordinated to the study of the new.

In order to establish continuity links in the study of new material with the studied, to include new knowledge in the system of previously learned, repeat those sections and questions that prepare children for the perception of new material. At such a lesson, the primary consolidation of the studied material also takes place.

The structure of this type of lesson is as follows:

- 1) repetition of the material necessary for the conscious assimilation of new knowledge,
- 2) message of the topic and purpose of the lesson,
- 3) learning new material,
- 4) verification of students' understanding of the studied material and its primary consolidation,
- 5) homework assignment.

Along with the specified specific tasks of the first lessons, special didactic tasks are also solved on them: to teach counting objects, to introduce numbers, letters and sounds, etc.

Non-standard lessons.

Recently, in many publications in scientific and pedagogical journals, as well as among teachers, the concept of the so-called "non-standard lesson" has become widespread, which includes "lessons-courts", "lessons-forums", "lessons-debates", "lessons-dialogues", "lessons-press conferences", "lessons-concerts" and the like.

There has been a lot of talk and writing about integral lessons lately. The study of various objects can be carried out in at least two ways. One of them is that the teacher, revealing the content of the educational material of his subject, attracts relevant information from other disciplines, uses the knowledge of students acquired by them in other lessons, implementing interdisciplinary connections.

In many cases, this approach justifies itself. Nevertheless, there are situations when the implementation of interdisciplinary connections by one teacher is difficult. This, in particular, happens when the teacher has to reveal those aspects of

multidimensional objects that are not included in the content of his subject, but without which it is impossible to form a holistic view of the object of study.

Integral lessons can be classified according to meaning and didactic purpose. Taking into account the unification of academic subjects, the material that is considered in the integral lesson, and determines its content, there are humanitarian, natural-mathematical, mixed classes. Each of them (depending on the anticipated didactic goal) can be attributed to one of the groups: lessons of learning new knowledge, lessons of systematization of generalization of knowledge, combined lessons.

The general structure of such classes includes: introduction - setting the goal, the task of the lesson, updating the basic knowledge necessary for the conscious perception of its content, communication of the work plan; the main part - disclosure of the content of the educational material; conclusion - summing up, evaluating the work of students, determining homework.

The main part of the lesson is more variable compared to the introduction and conclusion. This is due to many factors, namely: the objects of study are abstract and concrete; the characterization of some requires mainly a monological presentation of the teacher, others - the organization of a conversation with students; the course of reasoning can be deductive or inductive, not the least role is played by the individuality of the teacher.

In such classes, students receive deep, multifaceted knowledge about the object of study. Using information from different subjects, students comprehend events and phenomena in a new way. Thanks to this, opportunities for the synthesis of knowledge, the formation of students' skills to transfer knowledge from one area to another are expanding.

Non-standard lessons arouse keen interest in students, and interest, as you know, is a stimulus for cognition, motivates the learning process, turns the school from a "school of cramming" into a "school of joy", as great teachers of the past dreamed of it.

It is important to think about how to create an atmosphere of common interest in the lesson, a cheerful atmosphere that allows the whole class and each student individually to realize and feel creative co-friendship, the successes of comrades and their own, to experience the joy of learning. It is necessary to think over the question of preparing students for the lesson: what tools, counting or working material to bring, what observations to make at home, what to read in advance, etc.

When conducting a lesson, the teacher strives to fulfill the planned plan. However, if the case requires it, changes can be made to it during the lesson. For example, if all the exercises outlined in the plan are completed, but the material has not yet been assimilated by children to the extent necessary, then additional exercises are performed.

A daily analysis of one's own lessons from the point of view of what succeeded in the lesson and what failed, what is the reason for failure and what are the ways to overcome it, what needs to be further developed and consolidated, put into the piggy bank of experience, should become a teacher's need. Analyzing their own lessons, as well as attending lessons of experienced teachers with subsequent analysis of these lessons will help a young novice teacher master the art of conducting lessons.

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